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Methodology for environmental monitoring of CO₂ geological storage sites from Romania

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Abstract

Romania is committed to decrease CO₂ emissions and to achieve net zero emissions by 2050, as Member of European Union. Recent climate commitments, including the Green Deal and Net-Zero Industry Act, have led to an increase of interest for carbon capture and storage technology at national level. It is expected that the largest industrial CO₂ emitters will make further steps to develop CCS projects, taking into account, apart from the regulatory obligations, the rising price of CO₂ emission certificates. Furthermore, there is the opportunity to finance this type of projects within the Innovation Fund.

From a regulatory perspective, Romania has a legal framework for the safe storage of carbon dioxide, under the supervision of National Agency for Mineral Resources, the competent authority for oil and gas exploitation and CO₂ geological storage. Still, there is still work to be done also in this field and efforts are currently made to harmonize Petroleum Law with CO₂ Storage Law. Besides this regulatory opportunity and challenge in the same time, development of CCS projects needs also additional financial incentives and governmental support.

Taking into account the increased interest for CCS in Romania and considering that an actual CCS project will be soon developed, we have proposed and started a new project financed by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization, "Development of an Environmental Monitoring Methodology for Potential CO₂ Storage Sites in Romania" (PN 23300404). Through this project we aim to support future storage operators by developing an environmental monitoring methodology for onshore storage sites that will be tested and validated, in the absence of an actual CCS project, on natural analogues for storage of CO₂ (natural CO₂ fields) and analogues for CO₂ leakage (sites with natural CO₂ emissions).

The preliminary environmental monitoring methodology, already formulated in the first year of the project, has low implementation costs and it is based on a combination of monitoring methods, part of them being mature methods in the field of CO₂ monitoring such as the geochemical methods and near-surface seismic, and methods that still need some validation in this field, like GPR and resistivity methods. For each of these methods we have made preliminary implementation procedures, aimed to obtain maximum results for leakage detection in the near surface. These procedures will be implemented and tested comparatively on the selected natural fields, one CO₂ field and one field with natural CO₂ emissions.

Together with the formulation of the preliminary monitoring methodology and of specific implementation procedures of the included monitoring methods, we have already started the process of selecting the best candidates for test sites. The selection process was started with two field campaigns in spring and autumn 2023 aiming at localizing and verifying the local situation of the sites, including access to the sites, level of CO₂ emissions, existence of local operators, potential for further investigation and possible support from local authorities. From the collected data, both literature and field data, the best candidates are currently Bodoc (mineral water exploitation) and Lăzărești (natural CO₂ emissions due to post-volcanic activity).

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Further activities of the project include the final selection of the test sites, building the geological and geophysical models and testing of the developed monitoring methodology. Depending on the testing results, the methodology will be adjusted in order to maximize leakage detection. The results of the project will be gathered in a best practice guide for environmental monitoring of CO₂ geological storage sites in Romania to be used by the competent authorities in the field and by future storage operators.

Keywords: CO₂ storage, monitoring, natural analogues

1. Introduction

Romania is committed to decrease CO₂ emissions and to achieve net zero emissions by 2050, as Member of European Union. Recent climate commitments, including the Green Deal and Net-Zero Industry Act, have led to an increase of interest for carbon capture and storage technology at national level. It is expected that the largest industrial CO₂ emitters will make further steps to develop CCS (carbon capture and storage) projects, considering, apart from the regulatory obligations, the rising price of CO₂ emission certificates. Furthermore, there is the opportunity to finance this type of projects within the Innovation Fund.

From a regulatory perspective, Romania has a legal framework for the safe storage of carbon dioxide, under the supervision of National Regulatory Authority for Mining, Petroleum, and Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide (former National Agency for Mineral Resources), the competent authority for oil and gas exploitation and CO₂ geological storage. Besides this regulatory opportunity, development of CCS projects needs also additional financial incentives and governmental support. No CCS project is currently implemented into the country, but preparations are ongoing.

Considering the increased interest for CCS in Romania and considering that an actual CCS project will be soon developed, we have proposed and started a new project financed by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization, "Development of an Environmental Monitoring Methodology for Potential CO₂ Storage Sites in Romania" (PN 23300404). Through this project, with a four-year duration, we aim to support future storage operators by developing an environmental monitoring methodology for onshore storage sites that will be tested and validated, in the absence of an actual CCS project, on natural analogues for storage of CO₂ (natural CO₂ fields) and analogues for CO₂ leakage (sites with natural CO₂ emissions). In the first two years of the project, preliminary monitoring methodology has been formulated and the test sites have been selected.

2. Preliminary methodology for environmental monitoring of onshore storage sites

The preliminary environmental monitoring methodology includes geochemical, geophysical and ecosystem monitoring methods. The methodology has been designed to have a low implementation cost and includes mature methods in the field of CO₂ geological storage monitoring, but also methods that still need some validation. For each of the included methods, specific procedures for implementation have been formulated.

The geochemical methods are flux and soil gas monitoring, water and soil sampling. These are all methods proven to be able to highlight CO₂ leakage into the environment. This was demonstrated through the study of natural laboratories [1], but also from actual CO₂ storage projects.

Soil flux monitoring is a method that requires many sampling stations to be able to establish the natural variability of gas fluxes into the soil before the beginning of storage operation. It can also contribute to quantification of leakage rate, if needed.

Soil gas method refers to the evaluation of gas phase chemistry in the vadose zone, using in situ measurements or analysis of gas samples in a laboratory [1]. It is important, for CO₂ monitoring, to separate the natural variability of CO₂ gas coming from natural sources (e.g. plant root respiration, microbial oxidation of organic matter in the soil)

from anthropic CO₂ coming from a storage site. The technique offers precise measurements of CO₂ concentration in soil at depth, but for leakage detection it is important, apart from establishing the natural variability, the configuration of the survey grid. We propose that the soil gas surveys to be conducted on profiles intercepting the potential leakage pathways and failure points of the storage system. The sampling points on a profile should be placed at a distance of 2 to 5 m.

In the sampling points for soil gas monitoring and at the corresponding depth of the measurements, it is important to collect and analyze soil samples for a stronger correlation of anomalies with local conditions. Analysis of soil samples should be made in situ for pH and humidity and for other components (e.g. heavy metals) using X ray fluorescence and granulometric method. It is worth mentioning that in the literature, increase of heavy metals content was correlated with CO₂ leakage.

Water sampling and analysis is also an important monitoring method for CO₂ storage. Underground water (especially drinking water aquifers) quality is a major concern of the public and through careful monitoring it can be demonstrated that the storage operation did not produce any contamination. The following parameters should be analyzed: pH, conductivity, alkalinity, major chemical components, trace chemicals, stable isotope, radio isotopes and redox potential. The variation of these parameters (if the natural variation and background are well determined) in some cases could lead to the localization and to understanding the consequences of CO₂ migration. CO₂ migration into underground water can lead to decrease of pH and consequently to dissolution of more problematic constituents than CO₂. The major problem is the need for identifying local water wells and also to drill new ones in order to detect any leakage. Choosing the location of wells for water monitoring should be done in correlation with the leakage scenarios simulated within the storage project.

For ecosystem monitoring, vegetation surveys and microbiological ones should be included in the monitoring plan. Vegetative stress could be a good indicator for CO₂ leakage [1]. There are also bio-indicators for leakage, discovered through the study of natural laboratories. For this reasons it is important to deploy vegetation surveys on different seasons before the injection is started to establish the normal vegetation for an area and to detect in the future any substitution or absence of some species.

Elevated CO₂ concentrations have also an effect on microbial populations in the soil [2]. Microbiological monitoring of storage sites involves analyzing the microbiological communities present at different depths to determine any changes in the event of a leakage. These analyzes are recommended to be done in sensitive areas such as protected areas. The aim is usually the identification of species, the quantitative analysis of the microbial community, in close correlation with the CO₂ concentrations determined by soil-gas measurements.

The methodology of environmental monitoring can benefit also from geophysical methods, included in our research, such as gravimetry, near-surface seismics and resistivity methods.

3. Selection of best candidates for testing the methodology

After the formulation of our monitoring methodology, we have begun the selection of the test sites, one site with natural CO₂ emissions, analogue to a leaking storage site and one site with no emissions, analogue for a safe storage site.

After an extended literature review and consultation with specialists from mineral water companies, we have investigated as potential test areas mofetic CO₂ deposits – mineral water deposits and areas with natural CO₂ emissions. The water deposits documented and investigated in the field at the end of 2023 were: Talomir-Bodoc, Malnaș Băi, Bixad Olt, Siculeni, Dealul Bogat, Stânceni, Bilbor and Borsec. As a potential test site with natural CO₂ emissions, we investigated the Lăzărești site in the field. Apart from these, we have also previously investigated the opportunity to use as test site a natural CO₂ field, but due to restrictions to the site, this direction has not been further investigated.

Most of the studied area overlaps the eruptive chain area (Călimani-Gurghiu-Harghita) (Fig. 1), the crystalline-Mesozoic area and the flysch area, to which is added a smaller area of extension, which overlaps compartments belonging to the Transylvanian sedimentary basin.

Fig. 1. Delimitation of research areas of interest for environmental monitoring, in the post-volcanic area Călimani-Gurghiu-Harghita.

The final selection of the sites has been made based on taking into account the analogy for actual storage sites and the analogy with potentially leaking sites, the accessibility in the field, considerations on the logistics for future campaigns and also taking into account the support from local authorities.

As a natural analogue for CO₂ leakage into the environment, we selected the Lăzărești site. Among all the sites previously investigated and analyzed, it has a good location, presents good infrastructure elements, especially access (paved roads), and also features a perimeter with lower emissions south of the tourist-exploited mofette alignment. This low-emission perimeter has a good degree of analogy with potential CO₂ leakage from an anthropogenic reservoir. Another factor that led to the selection of this site is the support provided by the Cozmeni City Hall, which is extremely important for the realization of future campaigns.

As a natural analogue for storage integrity, we chose the Bodoc area, corresponding to the Talomir-Bodoc carbonated mineral water deposit. From the analysis of inventoried data, the CO₂ in the aquifer is naturally retained in the reservoir. It can be considered a good analogue to a saline aquifer in which CO₂ is injected and stored. The selection criteria, in addition to the degree of analogy with a saline aquifer, included the presence of infrastructure elements (site access via paved roads), the relatively shallow depth of the aquifer (suitable for the implementation of non-invasive investigation methods), and the support of local authorities.

Before the implementation and testing of preliminary environmental monitoring methodology, a preliminary evaluation has been made for the selected sites, in spring 2024. Within the Bodoc perimeter, measurements of greenhouse gas fluxes were conducted, along with 3 profiles of electrometry and photogrammetry. Within the Lăzărești perimeter, only greenhouse gas flux measurements were conducted in the southern part of the site, where a terracing was recently completed. Previous investigations have been made here starting with 2020, but mostly focused on northern perimeter with much higher emissions.

4. Preliminary evaluation of Bodoc site

4.1. Geological setting

The Bodoc area is located in the western extremity of the Cretaceous flysch zone (Fig. 2), intensely folded and faulted. The flysch deposits are comprised of an alternation of sandstones, marls, clays and conglomerates.

Fig. 2. Simplified relief map of the Olt valley between Malnaş and Sfântu Gheorghe area— adapted from Ghenea et al. (1971) showing the distribution of river terraces and location of Ghidfalău (GHI) profile. [3]

The geological-structural framework consists of the deposits of the Ceahlău nappe (Bodoc branching) that outcrop on the mountain area and the post-tectonic deposits that form the filling of the Bodoc-Malnaş depression, part of the Braşov basin [3]. The deposits relevant for our study (Sânmartin-Bodoc strata) are in the lower part of the succession in marl-sandstone flysch facies (lower part of Upper Barremian-Lower Albian series) and in the upper part in sandstone-conglomerate facies (upper part of Middle Albian series).

In the basement deposits, aquifer accumulations of medium depth are individualized, and in the upper part there are post-tectonic deposits of the cover, with aquifer accumulations of shallow depth [4]. The conglomerate facies located in a synclinal structure, is strongly affected by tectonic movements (a series of transverse faults), responsible for the migration of mineral waters to the surface.

The area selected for the natural analogue of storage integrity, a natural CO₂ reservoir, is located in the Talomir-Bodoc deposits area (Fig. 3), represented by a depressional area with altitudes of approximately 500 m and a mountainous area with altitudes of over 700 m.

Fig. 3. Geological profile through the Bodoc deposit [4]. 1. Alluvium of the low terrace (Holocene), 2. Alluvium of the 20 m terrace (Wurm), 3. Clays and sands (Upper Pliocene-Lower Pleistocene), 4. Sandy and conglomerate marl complex (Barremian-Aptian).

4.2. Soil flux measurements

Within the Bodoc perimeter, soil gas flux measurements (CO_2 , CH_4 and H_2S) were made with a West Systems portable flux meter equipped with CO_2 , CH_4 and H_2S sensors. A total of 43 stations were measured (Fig. 4 a), and the measurement points were chosen in areas considered representative of the perimeter and future field campaigns. The objective of the gas flow measurement campaign was to obtain an overview of the variation of gas emissions within the perimeter. As we expected, being a well-exploited mineral water deposit in the past, we did not identify any gas emission points. CO_2 flux (Fig. 4 b) varied between $122 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$ and $5264 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$. Higher CO_2 fluxes were recorded in the southern part of the perimeter. The CH_4 flux (Fig. 4 c) varied from $1.76 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$ to $2255 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$. The highest values, in this case, were measured in the northern part of the perimeter. The flux of H_2S (Fig. 4 d) varied very little, from $1.05 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$ to $10.09 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$. The variation of greenhouse gas fluxes will need to be confirmed by measurement campaigns over several seasons. It is important to exclude seasonal variation and implicitly to exclude variation due to biological activity that could have a significant impact on CO_2 and CH_4 flux values.

Fig. 4. Maps for measurements at Bodoc. a. Location of GHG sampling points and of the geo-electric surveys. b. Variation of CO_2 flux. c. Variation of CH_4 flux. d. Variation of H_2S flux.

4.3. Geoelectrical survey

The geoelectrical survey was conducted using an AGI Ministing resistivimeter. 3 geoelectrical profiles were measured (Fig. 4 a and Fig. 5) through Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES), Schlumberger array type. The distance between the profiles was 2 meters and each of them consisted of 14 VES. With a profile length of 46 meters, the maximum investigation depth was calculated at 4.2 meters. Data processing was made with AGI Earth Imager 2D/3D software.

Fig. 5. Measured electrical profiles at Bodoc site

Fig. 6. 3D resistivity model

The geoelectrical investigation, especially the resistivity model (Fig. 6), highlighted that the presence of clay content tends to reduce the increase of resistivity caused by the displacement of water by less conductive CO_2 . As a result, CO_2 saturations estimated from resistivity measurements without any correction for the clay effect are considerably lower than the actual saturations. It is important to realize, however, that the resistivity values are an index tool that must be correlated or calibrated to site-specific soil measurement through water and soil sampling.

4.4. Photogrammetry

For the photogrammetry survey, the drone used was a DJI Phantom 4 PRO V2.0 quadcopter (that is equipped with 3 axes motorized gimbal and a 1-inch 20 MP CMOS sensor with a mechanical shutter), a Trimble R2 GNSS system and a set of 9 targets (GCP – ground control points) used to improve positioning and elevation accuracy. The flight plan was executed on a Dell rugged laptop, via DJI's Terra software, in which the following flight/camera parameters were implied:

- Flight altitude – 65 m
- Side/forward photograph overlap – 75%/85%
- Gimbal pitch – 90° (Nadir) – the camera axis is perpendicular to the ground/object;
- Camera settings – $f/5.6$, a fast shutter speed of $1/2400$ s, a fixed ISO at 100 and camera focus set to manual.

The mapping process was completed by analysing and processing the 2D photographs, captured by the camera, in dedicated software – Agisoft Metashape. The result was the digital terrain model which will be extremely important for the future field campaigns.

Fig. 7. Digital terrain model made for Bodoc site

5. Preliminary evaluation of Lăzărești site

5.1. Geological setting

The site at Lăzărești is located on a succession of deposits, starting with the Cretaceous flysch (layers of Sânmartin-Bodoc, Barremian-Albian) (Fig. 8) at the base, up to terrace deposits. The alluvial deposits consist of blocks, sandy gravels with rounded elements ranging from 2 to 40 cm in diameter. The elements are predominantly composed of

andesites, and less frequently of limestones, sandstones, and crystalline schists. Coarse alluvial deposits are locally covered or found at the base of slopes with finer alluvium, including fine sands and sandy clays, marls, and gray clays. Alluvial deposits formed during the Early Quaternary (debris cones and upper terraces at +20-25 m and 35-40 m). In the Late Quaternary, lower terraces and the floodplain of the Olt River were formed, along with the floodplains of the Cozmeni, Tușnad, and Hipotoc streams (including the tributary Valea Pârâului, Lăzărești) [3], [4], etc. Terrace deposits are composed of gravels and sands, with slightly rounded volcanic (andesitic) elements. Locally, sandy lenses or even sandy horizons are present [3].

Fig. 8. Geological map of the Eastern Carpathians [5], with the perimeter of the selected study area Lăzărești

In the southern perimeter of the Ciuc basin, in the Tușnad-Lăzărești area, large amounts of sands of 20-80 m thickness accumulated during the Early Quaternary, with a dominant sandy fraction of 80-91%. These deposits have been exploited through quarries (Pásztohy Zoltán - Hydrogeological Study - PUZ Ciomatu Mare – Saint Ana Lake, Harghita County) [4].

The Lăzărești site is located axially on a spilled anticline (Fig. 9), with a north-south direction, which expresses a tectonic relief of this kind, thus resulting in some forms of derived structures such as small valleys or depressions of anticlines, buttonholes, ridges, etc. To the east, a second spilled anticline is highlighted, with the same direction, north-south, and between them a syncline develops, with a north-south direction.

Fig. 9. Geological section north of the Lăzărești site, in the V-E direction [6]

The Lăzărești hydromineral area is a very rich and varied perimeter with carbonated mineral springs and mofettas spread in the Tușnad, Hipotoc valleys. Most of the springs appear to the present day through the proluvial-deluvial and alluvial deposits from the sandstone and marl series of the Sânmartin-Bodoc strata (Barremian-Albian). Due to the complex structure of the foundation through which the gas-enriched waters circulate, the flow rates of the springs show large variations, and the concentration of the mineral waters is variable, because of dilution [6], [7].

In areas with carbonated and sulphurous mineral waters, aggressive manifestations may occur for the deposits crossed, due to the acidic nature, generated by sulfuric and/or carbonic solutions [6], [7]. Groundwater levels are high during periods of heavy rain or in spring after snowmelt due to uplift, which by saturating the foundation lands with water, through liquefaction can reduce the stability of buildings or works of art. Liquefaction processes may be more pronounced in areas with fine sandy deposits in the Tușnad-Lăzărești perimeter.

5.2. Soil flux survey

The measurements of greenhouse gas fluxes (CO_2 , CH_4 , and H_2S) were made using the same portable flux meter from West Systems. A total of 18 stations were measured (Fig. 10), with 6 points considered representative for each of the 3 terraces. The objective of the gas flux measurement campaign was to obtain an overview of the variation in gas emissions in the southern part of the Lăzărești site. The northern area, with high emissions and tourist mofettes, had been previously investigated, and we already have an overview of the emission variations for it.

The CO_2 flux (Fig. 10 b) varied between $166.4 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$ and $18070 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$, with the highest value measured on the intermediate terrace. The CH_4 flux (Fig. 10 c) varied very little, with very low values, from $2.403 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$ to $14.690 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$. The H_2S flux (Fig. 10 d) also varied very little, from $1.941 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$ to $6.105 \text{ mol/m}^2/\text{day}$. The variation in greenhouse gas fluxes needs to be confirmed through measurement campaigns in multiple seasons. It is important to exclude seasonal variation and, implicitly, the variation due to biological activity, which could have a significant impact on the CO_2 and CH_4 flux values.

Fig. 10. Maps for soil flux measurements at Lăzărești site. a. Location of sampling points. b. Variation of CO₂ flux. c. Variation of CH₄ flux. d. Variation of H₂S flux.

6. Conclusions

The preliminary environmental monitoring methodology for CO₂ storage sites has been made and includes mature methods and less-used methods for near surface investigation. This methodology will be refined in the upcoming 2 years following testing and validation in the field, at two test sites, selected from potential natural analogues and laboratories.

The two test sites are quite opposite, one is an analogue for a leaking site, Lăzărești, and one is an analogue for safe storage, a natural mineral water reservoir, Bodoc. Through their differences, we hope to refine our methodology and formulate a final one, suitable to be used as a viable solution for future storage sites from Romania. The

comparative assessment and analysis of the sites will allow also a better understanding of leakage mechanisms and safe storage concept.

Following a preliminary assessment made through field measurements, the analogy with desired models have been confirmed. Soil flux surveys have highlighted the natural emissions at Lăzărești, but also the absence of emissions at Bodoc.

Testing of the methodology has been started at the sites in autumn 2024 and will continue throughout 2025 and early 2026. For the geochemical methods implied, together with ecosystem surveys, this will allow determine also the natural variability of the measured parameters.

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